

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

Google Scholar

SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Nurlanova Diana

OLMOSH VA UNING MA'NO TURLARI.PRONOLIMANIZATSIYA

DRJI

Universal
Impact Factor

WEBSITE:WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

2023-2024

zenodo

ADVANCED SCIENCE INDEX

EMAIL:INFO@REANDPUB.UZ